

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_2_2	
Title	Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) investigations.
Category	Environmental /Socio-cultural.
Purpose of the method	Gathering ecological information about biodiversity, ecosystem benefits, socio-cultural environmental resources, ect.. thanks to the knowledge owned and shared by the residents and/or specific target groups.
Effort in time	Usually, the time required for one interview is limited to half hour.
Number of objects investigated	Usually, the minimum number of interviews is defined depending on the topic.
Data format	Qualitative, quantitative, geospatial, temporal.
Description	<p>Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK) represents the accumulation, which has been going on for some time, of knowledge, practices, and beliefs regarding the relationships between living beings in a specific ecosystem. This knowledge is acquired by indigenous human populations over hundreds or thousands of years through direct contact with the environment, passed down from generation to generation, and used for subsistence. LEK encompasses the links between people, plants, animals, natural phenomena, and landscapes, and the timing of events for activities such as hunting, fishing, trapping, agriculture, and forestry. It also encompasses a people's worldview, including ecology, spirituality, human-animal relationships, and more.</p> <p>Data from Local Ecological Knowledge is obtained by standardised questionnaires and in-person interviews with the locals involved. Results are tabulated (e.g., in Microsoft Excel[®]). Qualitative, quantitative and temporal tabulated data are processed with statistical software (e.g., R for statistics). When spatial information is available, data is processed in Geo-spatial Information System (GIS) environments.</p>
Basic Literature	<p>IPBES. (2022). Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Zenodo.</p> <p>Newman, R. (2021). Human Dimensions: Traditional Ecological Knowledge—Finding a Home in the Ecological Society of America. The Bulletin of the Ecological Society of America, 102(3).</p>

Contact person within the project	Maurizio Pinna, maurizio.pinna@unisalento.it, PP10 – UniSal Scientific Responsible, CS2 – Aquatina di Frigole Protected Area Scientific Responsible. Francesco Zangaro, francesco.zangaro@unisalento.it, PP10 – UniSal Scientific Team. Valeria Specchia, valeria.specchia@unisalento.it, PP10 – UniSal Scientific Team.
Linked material	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6417333 https://doi.org/10.1002/bes2.1892